

On Novel Mid-point type inequalities through twice-differentiable functions on tempered fractional integrals

Ashok Kumar Sahoo^{1,a,b}, Bibhakar Kodamasingh^{2,b}, Bharat Keshari Swain^{3*,c}

^aDepartment of Mathematics, Trident Academy of
Technology, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha, India

^bDepartment of Mathematics, Institute of Technical Education and Research, Siksha 'O'
Anusandhan deemed to be University, Bhubaneswar, 751030, Odisha, India

^cDepartment Of Mathematics, Agarpara College, Agarpara, 756115, Bhadrak, Odisha,
India

Abstract: In this paper, we introduce a novel equality involving tempered fractional integrals for twice-differentiable functions and employ it to establish a variety of left and right-sided Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities within the framework of tempered fractional calculus. Several special cases of the derived theorems are presented to demonstrate the applicability and versatility of the results. The proposed approach offers a clear and straightforward methodology for handling fractional inequalities, making it accessible for further theoretical developments and practical applications in mathematical analysis.

Keyword: Hermite-Hadamard inequalities; Midpoint inequality; Tempered fractional integrals; Convex functions; Twice differentiable functions.

1 Introduction

C. Hermite and J. Hadamard introduced Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities for convex functions. Let us consider that $g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function on the interval I of real numbers, and $\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1 \in I$ with $\hat{c}_1 < \hat{d}_1$. Then the following inequality holds:

$$g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \leq \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1) + g(\hat{d}_1)}{2} \quad (1)$$

If the function g is concave, then the inequalities in (1) hold in the opposite direction. Numerous studies have been devoted to establishing midpoint and trapezoidal-type inequalities, which provide estimates for the lower and upper bounds of the two sides of inequality (1), respectively. For example, Dragomir and Agarwal first proved trapezoid-type inequalities for the case of convex functions in [12] and Kirmaci first derived midpoint-type inequalities for convex functions in [18]. Iqbal *et al.* [16] investigated some fractional Midpoint-type inequalities for convex functions. Sarikaya *et al.* generalized (1) for fractional integrals. The authors also investigated some corresponding trapezoidal-type inequalities in [35]. Moreover, in [11] Dragomir proved Hermite-Hadamard type

forcoordinated convex functions. In addition to this, Trapezoid and midpoint type for coordinated convex functions were established in [34] and [19] respectively. Moreover, in [37], various fractional midpoint-type inequalities were derived for coordinated convex functions. In addition, they proved Hermite-Hadamard inequalities and different trapezoid and midpoint type inequalities for generalized fractional integrals. We take to [8,10,27] for further information about these kinds of inequalities.

Some Hermite-Hadamard and Simpson-type inequalities were established for functions whose absolute values of derivatives are convex in [31]. Barani et al. [6] proved Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities for twice differentiable convex functions. Park considered new estimates in generalization of Hadamard, Ostrowski and Simpson-type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives in absolute value at certain powers are convex and quasiconvex functions. Moreover, some new generalized fractional integral inequalities of midpoint and trapezoid-type for twice differentiable convex functions are obtained in [24]. Furthermore, in [7], Budak et al. established some midpoint and trapezoid type inequalities for functions whose second derivative in absolute value are convex. For related results involving such inequalities applied to twice differentiable functions, refer to [15, 32, 33]. Several researchers have explored fractional integral inequalities and their applications through the use of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. For example, a variant of Hermite-Hadamard inequalities of Riemann–Liouville fractional integral forms was investigated in [30]. Moreover, in [14], some left Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities were derived for Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. See [13,17,23] and the references therein for further information and properties of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. Although many mathematicians have investigated Hermite–Hadamard inequalities in the context of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals, several authors have also extended these studies to other forms of fractional integrals, including k -fractional, Hadamard, tempered and conformable fractional integrals. For example, we refer the reader to [1-5,26] and the references cited therein.

Tempered fractional calculus represents an extension of classical fractional calculus, incorporating exponential tempering to better model real-world processes with finite memory or bounded domains. In [9], the definitions of fractional integration with exponential kernels and weak singular were firstly reported in Buschman's earlier work. For alternative definitions of tempered fractional integrals, readers are referred to the texts [22, 29, 36] and the references cited therein. In [25], different Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities were derived associated with tempered fractional integrals for convex functions which covers the previously published results for Riemann integrals and Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals.

Objective: The primary aim of this study is to derive and prove left-sided Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. We begin by establishing a key identity for tempered fractional integrals of twice-differentiable functions. This identity is then used to develop midpoint-type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives satisfy convexity conditions. Beyond classical convexity, the analysis is extended to encompass a range of generalized convexity classes, including s -convex, m -convex, log-convex, quasi-convex, and preinvex functions,

thereby significantly broadening the scope of applicability of the derived results.

Novelty: This work integrates tempered fractional calculus with Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities for both classical and generalized convex function classes. The use of tempered fractional integrals introduces an exponential decay factor, enhancing modeling flexibility for systems with fading memory effects. Our results generalize several known inequalities and provide a unified approach that accommodates a variety of convexity frameworks under a single theoretical setting.

Significance: The derived inequalities not only extend the classical Hermite–Hadamard framework but also provide a versatile analytical tool for different convexity classes in fractional settings.

This generalization allows for sharper and more adaptable bounds in mathematical analysis, while also bridging the gap between fractional and classical inequalities. The inclusion of multiple convexity types highlights the robustness and adaptability of the proposed method.

Potential Applications

The findings in this work have potential applications in:

Applied Analysis: Extending analytical bounds in integral inequalities for generalized convexity classes.

Numerical Analysis: Improving error estimates for numerical integration methods involving tempered kernels.

Optimization Theory: Establishing new bounds in convex and generalized convex optimization problems under fractional settings.

Mathematical Modeling: Modeling real-world processes with both fractional dynamics and exponential decay, including viscoelastic materials, anomalous diffusion, heat conduction with memory effects, and processes governed by non-standard convexity structures.

2 Preliminaries:

We now introduce the necessary mathematical preliminaries from fractional calculus theory, which will be used in the rest of this paper.

Definition 1. Let $g \in L^1(\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1)$, where $\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\hat{c}_1 < \hat{d}_1$. The fractional α -order Riemann–Liouville integrals $J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^\alpha g$ and $J_{\hat{c}_1^-}^\alpha g$ are defined as

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^\alpha g(\hat{t}) = \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{t}} (\hat{t} - u)^{\alpha-1} g(u) du, \quad \hat{t} > \hat{c}_1, \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\hat{c}_1^-}^\alpha g(\hat{t}) = \int_{\hat{t}}^{\hat{d}_1} (u - \hat{t})^{\alpha-1} g(u) du, \quad \hat{t} < \hat{d}_1. \quad (3)$$

Here, $J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^0 g(\hat{t}) = J_{\hat{c}_1^-}^0 g(\hat{t}) = g(\hat{t})$, and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-x} x^{\alpha-1} dx.$$

Remark 1. Putting $\alpha = 1$, the fractional integral becomes the classical integral.

Definition 2. The incomplete Gamma function and the λ -incomplete Gamma function are defined, respectively, as

$$\Gamma(\alpha, \hat{t}) = \int_0^{\hat{t}} u^{\alpha-1} e^{-u} du, \quad \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \hat{t}) = \int_0^{\hat{t}} u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda u} du,$$

where $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Remark 2. (see[25]).For the real numbers $\alpha > 0, \hat{t}, \lambda \geq 0$, and $\hat{c}_1 < \hat{d}_1$, we have

$$\Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1}{2} \right) = \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u}{2}} du = \frac{2}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1}{2} \right)$$

$$\int_0^1 \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1 \cdot \hat{t}) \hat{t} d\hat{t} = \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha} - \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 3. (See [20,21]) The fractional tempered integral operators $J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g$ and $J_{\hat{c}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g$ of order $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ are given by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{t}) = \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{t}} (\hat{t} - u)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{t}-u)} g(u) du, \quad \hat{t} \in [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1], \tag{4}$$

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\hat{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{t}) = \int_{\hat{t}}^{\hat{d}_1} (u - \hat{t})^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(u-\hat{t})} g(u) du, \quad \hat{t} \in [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]. \tag{5}$$

These definitions hold for $g \in L^1(\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1)$.

Remark 3. If we take $\lambda = 0$, then the fractional integrals in (4) and (5) reduce to the Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals Fractional integral in (2) and (3), respectively.

3 Main results

In this section, we present various tempered fractional midpoint-type inequalities for twice-differentiable functions. To establish these inequalities, we begin with the following identity.

Lemma 1. Let $g : [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be absolutely continuous on (\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1) , and suppose $g'' \in L^1(\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1)$. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[\int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} g(d_1) + \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{c}_1} g(\hat{c}_1) \right] - g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \\ &= \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2 \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \sum_{k=1}^4 I_k. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{1/2} \chi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) g''(un + (1 - \nu)\hat{c}_1) du, \\ I_2 &= \int_{1/2}^1 \chi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) g''(um + (1 - \nu)\hat{d}_1) du, \\ I_3 &= \int_0^{1/2} \xi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) g''(un + (1 - \nu)\hat{c}_1) du, \\ I_4 &= \int_{1/2}^1 \xi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) g''(um + (1 - \nu)\hat{d}_1) du, \end{aligned}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) &= \nu \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \nu) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, \nu), \\ \xi_\alpha(\lambda, \nu) &= \nu \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \nu) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, \nu) - \nu \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1) + \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, 1). \end{aligned}$$

With the help of integration by parts, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &= \int_0^{1/2} [v\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, v)] g''(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du & (7) \\
 &= (v\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, v)) \frac{g'(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1)^{1/2}}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \int_0^{1/2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v) g'(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du \\
 &= \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1/2) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, 1/2) g' \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v) g(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1)^{1/2}}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \int_0^{1/2} u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du \\
 &= \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1/2) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, 1/2) g' \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \\
 &\quad - \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1/2)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^{1/2} u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &= \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{1}{2}) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, \frac{1}{2}) g' \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} - \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{1}{2})}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^{1/2} u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{d}_1) du & (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 = & -\frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha + 1, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1) + \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, 1) g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_4 = & \frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha + 1, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1) + \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha + 1, 1) g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(um + (1 - v)\hat{d}_1) du
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Adding (7)-(10), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=1}^4 I_k = & \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{c}_1) du \\
 & + \frac{1}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)u} g(un + (1 - v)\hat{d}_1) du - \frac{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 = & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha+2}} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t - \hat{c}_1)} g(t) dt \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha+2}} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - t)} g(t) dt - \frac{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right) \\
 = & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha+2}} \left[J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{d}_1) + J_{\hat{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{c}_1) \right] - \frac{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2} g \left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Multiplying both sides of (11) by

$$\frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)},$$

we recover equation (6), thereby completing the proof of Lemma 1.

Theorem 1. *Assume the assumptions of Lemma 1 hold. If $|g''|$ is convex on the interval $[\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$, then the following midpoint-type inequality holds:*

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^+} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^-} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right] \\ \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} [u_1(\lambda, \alpha) + u_2(\lambda, \alpha)] (|g''(\hat{c}_1)| + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|)$$

Here,

$$u_1(\lambda, \alpha) = \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du, \quad u_2(\lambda, \alpha) = \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du. \tag{12}$$

Proof: Taking the modulus of both sides of equation (6) and applying the triangle inequality yields:

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^+} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^-} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right] \\ \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(un + (1-v)\hat{c}_1)| du \\ + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(um + (1-v)\hat{d}_1)| du + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(un + (1-v)\hat{c}_1)| du \\ + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(um + (1-v)\hat{d}_1)| du \tag{13}$$

Now, using the convexity of $|g''|$, we apply the property:

$$|g''(t)| \leq v|g''(\hat{d}_1)| + (1-v)|g''(\hat{c}_1)| \quad \text{for all } t \in [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1],$$

and estimate each term accordingly. This leads to:

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^+} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)}_{\hat{c}_1^-} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right] \\ \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| [v|g''(\hat{d}_1)| + (1-v)|g''(\hat{c}_1)|] du \\ + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| [v|g''(\hat{c}_1)| + (1-v)|g''(\hat{d}_1)|] du \\ + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| [v|g''(\hat{d}_1)| + (1-v)|g''(\hat{c}_1)|] du \\ + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| [v|g''(\hat{c}_1)| + (1-v)|g''(\hat{d}_1)|] du \tag{#}$$

Grouping similar terms and simplifying gives:

$$= \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du |g''(\hat{c}_1)| + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|$$

This ends the proof of Theorem 1. □

Remark 3: If we set $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1, then the following midpoint-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha} \left[J^\alpha g(\hat{d}_1) + J^\alpha g(\hat{c}_1) \right] - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \\ & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2(\alpha + 1)} \left[\frac{1}{\alpha + 2} + \frac{\alpha - 3}{8} \right] \left[|g''(\hat{c}_1)| + |g''(\hat{d}_1)| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Which is established in [14, Theorem 2.2].

Remark 4: If we choose $\alpha = 1$ and $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1, then the classical midpoint-type inequality follows:

$$\frac{1}{\hat{d} - \hat{c}} \int_{\hat{c}}^{\hat{d}} g(u) du - g\left(\frac{\hat{c} + \hat{d}}{2}\right) \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{48} \left[|g''(\hat{c})| + |g''(\hat{d})| \right].$$

This result is given in Theorem 5 [33].

Theorem 2 Assume the assumptions of Lemma 1 hold. Moreover, if $|g''|^q$, with $q > 1$, is convex on $[\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$, then we have the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{c}_1) \right] - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \\ & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[\int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1/p} du + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1/p} du \right] \\ & \quad \times \left[\frac{3|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q}{8} + \frac{3|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q}{8} \right]^{1/q} \\ & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2^{3/q-1} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1)} \left[\int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \right]^{1/p} \\ & \quad \left[|g''(\hat{c}_1)| + |g''(\hat{d}_1)| \right], \end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Proof Let us first apply Holder's inequality in (13). Then we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(d_1 - c_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(d_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(c_1) \right] - g\left(\frac{c_1 + d_1}{2}\right) \\
 & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_0^{1/2} |g''(u_n + (1 - v)c_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_0^{1/2} |g''(u_m + (1 - v)d_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_{1/2}^1 |g''(u_n + (1 - v)c_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_{1/2}^1 |g''(u_m + (1 - v)d_1)|^q du
 \end{aligned}$$

By using the convexity of $|g''|^q$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(d_1 - c_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(d_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(c_1) \right] - g\left(\frac{c_1 + d_1}{2}\right) \\
 & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \times \\
 & \quad \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_0^{1/2} v|g''(d_1)|^q + (1 - v)|g''(c_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_0^{1/2} v|g''(c_1)|^q + (1 - v)|g''(d_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_{1/2}^1 v|g''(d_1)|^q + (1 - v)|g''(c_1)|^q du \\
 & \quad + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \int_{1/2}^1 v|g''(c_1)|^q + (1 - v)|g''(d_1)|^q dv
 \end{aligned}$$

This simplifies to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(d_1 - c_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left[J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(d_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(c_1) \right] - g\left(\frac{c_1 + d_1}{2}\right) \\
 & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(d_1 - c_1)(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^p du \\
 & \quad \times \left[\frac{3|g''(d_1)|^q + |g''(c_1)|^q}{8} \right]^{1/q} + \left[\frac{3|g''(c_1)|^q + |g''(d_1)|^q}{8} \right]^{1/q}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$\hat{c}_{11} = |g'(c_1)|^q, \quad \hat{d}_{11} = 3|g'(d_1)|^q, \quad \hat{c}_{12} = 3|g'(c_1)|^q, \quad \hat{d}_{12} = |g'(d_1)|^q$$

for the proof of the second inequality.

Using the fact that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (\hat{c}_{1k} + \hat{d}_{1k})^r \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \hat{c}_{1k}^r + \sum_{k=1}^n \hat{d}_{1k}^r, \quad \text{for } 0 \leq r < 1$$

and the inequality

$$1 + 3^{1/q} \leq 4,$$

the desired results of Theorem 2 can be obtained straightforwardly.

Remark 5 Let us put $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 2. Then, the following midpoint-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(d_1 - c_1)^{\alpha+1}} \left| J_{c_1^+}^\alpha g(d_1) + J_{d_1^-}^\alpha g(c_1) - g\left(\frac{c_1 + d_1}{2}\right) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)} \frac{1}{2^{\rho(1+\alpha)+1}(\rho(1 + \alpha) + 1)} + \int_{1/2}^1 u^{\alpha+1} - (1 + \alpha)u + \alpha^\rho du \\ & \times \frac{3|g''(d_1)|^q + |g''(c_1)|^q}{8}^{1/q} + \frac{3|g''(c_1)|^q + |g''(d_1)|^q}{8}^{1/q} \\ & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{2^{3/q-1}(\alpha + 1)} \frac{1}{2^{\rho(1+\alpha)+1}(\rho(1 + \alpha) + 1)} + \int_{1/2}^1 u^{\alpha+1} - (1 + \alpha)u + \alpha^\rho du \\ & \times |g''(c_1)| + |g''(d_1)|. \end{aligned}$$

Which is established in [14, Theorem 2.5].

Remark 6 If we put $\alpha = 1$ and $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 2, then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{d_1 - c_1} \left| \int_{c_1}^{d_1} g(u) du - g\left(\frac{c_1 + d_1}{2}\right) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{16} \frac{1}{2\rho + 1} \frac{1}{4} \left(3|g''(d_1)|^q + |g''(c_1)|^q \right)^{1/q} + \frac{3|g''(c_1)|^q + |g''(d_1)|^q}{4}^{1/q} \\ & \leq \frac{(d_1 - c_1)^2}{16} \frac{4}{2\rho + 1} |g''(c_1)| + |g''(d_1)|. \end{aligned}$$

Which are presented in [7, corollary 4.8].

Theorem 3 Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 1 hold. If $|g''|^q$, $q > 1$, is convex on $[\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left| J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} (v_1(\lambda, \alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left| g''(\hat{d}_1) \right|^q v_3(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q (v_1(\lambda, \alpha) - v_3(\lambda, \alpha))^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q v_3(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q (v_1(\lambda, \alpha) - v_3(\lambda, \alpha))^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + (v_2(\lambda, \alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left| g''(\hat{d}_1) \right|^q v_4(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q (v_2(\lambda, \alpha) - v_4(\lambda, \alpha))^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q v_4(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q (v_2(\lambda, \alpha) - v_4(\lambda, \alpha))^{\frac{1}{q}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $v_1(\lambda, \alpha)$ and $v_2(\lambda, \alpha)$ are defined in equation (12), and

$$v_3(\lambda, \alpha) = \int_0^{1/2} v |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du, \quad v_4(\lambda, \alpha) = \int_{1/2}^1 v |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| du.$$

Proof. By applying the power-mean inequality in equation (13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left| J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(u_n + (1-v)\hat{c}_1)|^q du \\ & + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(u_m + (1-v)\hat{d}_1)|^q du \\ & + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(u_n + (1-v)\hat{c}_1)|^q du \\ & + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)| |g''(u_m + (1-v)\hat{d}_1)|^q du. \end{aligned}$$

It is known that $|g''|^q$ is convex. Then, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha \Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left[J_{\hat{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{d}_1) + J_{\hat{c}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right] \\
 & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \\
 & \left[\int_{1/2}^1 |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_{1/2}^1 |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^h v |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + (1-v) |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q du \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_0^{1/2} |\chi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^h v |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + (1-v) |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q du \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^h v |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + (1-v) |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q du \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_{1/2}^1 |\xi_\alpha(\lambda, v)|^h v |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + (1-v) |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q du \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & = \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2\Gamma_\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)(\alpha, 1)} \left[(v_1(\lambda, \alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} (|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q v_3(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q (v_1(\lambda, \alpha) - v_3(\lambda, \alpha)))^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + (|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q v_4(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q (v_1(\lambda, \alpha) - v_3(\lambda, \alpha)))^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + (v_4(\lambda, \alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} (|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q v_4(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q (v_4(\lambda, \alpha) - v_4(\lambda, \alpha)))^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + (|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q v_4(\lambda, \alpha) + |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q (v_4(\lambda, \alpha) - v_4(\lambda, \alpha)))^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 7. Putting $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 3, we obtain the following midpoint-type inequality:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha} \left[J^{\alpha} g(\hat{d}_1) + J^{\alpha} g(\hat{c}_1) - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \right] \\
 & \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{2(\alpha + 1)} \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+2}(\alpha + 2)} \cdot \frac{(\alpha + 2)|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + (\alpha + 4)|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q}{2(\alpha + 3)} \\
 & + \frac{(\alpha + 2)|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + (\alpha + 4)|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q}{2(\alpha + 3)} \\
 & + \psi_1(\alpha)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\psi_2(\alpha) |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + (\psi_1(\alpha) - \psi_2(\alpha)) |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \psi_2(\alpha)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\psi_1(\alpha) |g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + (\psi_1(\alpha) - \psi_2(\alpha)) |g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}},
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\psi_1(\alpha) = \frac{2^{\alpha+2} - 1}{2^{\alpha+2}(\alpha + 2)} + \frac{\alpha - 3}{8}, \quad \psi_2(\alpha) = \frac{2^{\alpha+3} - 1}{2^{\alpha+3}(\alpha + 3)} + \frac{2\alpha - 7}{24}.$$

This result coincides with [14, Theorem 2.7].

Remark 8. If we put $\alpha = 1$ and $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 3, then we have the midpoint-type inequality:

$$\frac{1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} g(u) du - g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \leq \frac{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^2}{48} \cdot \frac{3|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q + 5|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q}{8} \frac{1}{q} + \frac{3|g''(\hat{c}_1)|^q + 5|g''(\hat{d}_1)|^q}{8} \frac{1}{q}.$$

Which is described in [31, Proposition 5].

Right-Sided Hermite-Hadamard Inequality via Tempered Fractional Integrals

Theorem 3.1. Let $g : [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $\lambda \geq 0$. Then the following inequality involving the right-sided tempered fractional integral holds:

$$g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha} \leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1-t)} g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1) + g(\hat{d}_1)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

Proof. Since g is convex on $[\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$, we have for all $t \in [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$:

$$g(t) \geq g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right),$$

and

$$g(t) \leq \frac{\hat{d}_1 - t}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{c}_1) + \frac{t - \hat{c}_1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{d}_1).$$

Define the right-sided tempered fractional integral:

$$I := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1-t)} g(t) dt.$$

Lower bound:

Using $g(t) \geq g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right)$, we get:

$$I \geq g\left(\frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1-t)} dt.$$

Make the substitution $s = \hat{d}_1 - t$, then:

$$I \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} s^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda s} ds = g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}.$$

Using the identity:

$$\Gamma(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1) = \frac{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1}{2} \Gamma(\alpha, 1),$$

we conclude:

$$I \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

Upper bound:

From the convexity bound:

$$g(t) \leq \frac{\hat{d}_1 - t}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{c}_1) + \frac{t - \hat{c}_1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{d}_1),$$

we write:

$$I \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1)}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^\alpha e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - t)} dt + \frac{g(\hat{d}_1)}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (\hat{d}_1 - t)^{\alpha-1} (t - \hat{c}_1) e^{-\lambda(\hat{d}_1 - t)} dt.$$

Evaluating these integrals via substitution and known identities, we get:

$$I \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1) + g(\hat{d}_1)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

This completes the proof. □

Left-Sided Hermite-Hadamard Inequality via Tempered Fractional Integrals

Theorem 3.2. Let $g : [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $\lambda \geq 0$. Then the following inequality involving the left-sided tempered fractional integral holds:

$$g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha} \leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t - \hat{c}_1)} g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1) + g(\hat{d}_1)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

Proof. Since g is convex on $[\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$, for all $t \in [\hat{c}_1, \hat{d}_1]$:

$$g(t) \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2},$$

and

$$g(t) \leq \frac{\hat{d}_1 - t}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{c}_1) + \frac{t - \hat{c}_1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{d}_1).$$

Define the left-sided tempered fractional integral:

$$I := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\hat{c}_1)} g(t) dt.$$

Lower bound:

Using $g(t) \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2}$, we get:

$$I \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\hat{c}_1)} dt.$$

Substitute $s = t - \hat{c}_1$, so when $t = \hat{c}_1$, $s = 0$, and when $t = \hat{d}_1$, $s = \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1$. Then:

$$I \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} s^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda s} ds = g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}.$$

Using:

$$\Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1) = \frac{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1}{2} \Gamma_\lambda(\alpha, 1),$$

we obtain:

$$I \geq g \frac{\hat{c}_1 + \hat{d}_1}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

Upper bound:

From convexity:

$$g(t) \leq \frac{\hat{d}_1 - t}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{c}_1) + \frac{t - \hat{c}_1}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} g(\hat{d}_1).$$

Then:

$$I \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1)}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\hat{c}_1)} dt + \frac{g(\hat{d}_1)}{\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\hat{c}_1}^{\hat{d}_1} (t - \hat{c}_1)^{\alpha-1} (\hat{d}_1 - t) e^{-\lambda(t-\hat{c}_1)} dt.$$

Substituting $s = t - \hat{c}_1$ and simplifying using known integral identities leads to:

$$I \leq \frac{g(\hat{c}_1) + g(\hat{d}_1)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\hat{d}_1 - \hat{c}_1)^\alpha}.$$

This completes the proof. □

Further Directions: Generalization to Broader Function Classes

To extend the Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities beyond twice-differentiable functions, one can consider the following function classes:

- Convex functions
- s-Convex functions
- Quasi-convex functions
- m-Convex functions
- Log-convex functions
- Preinvex functions

Hermite–Hadamard Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Integrals

1. For Convex Functions

Theorem 3.3. Let $f: [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function and $f \in L^1([\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1])$. Then for $\alpha > 0$, the Hermite–Hadamard type inequality via the left and right tempered fractional integrals is given by:

$$f \frac{\check{c}_1 + \check{d}_1}{2} \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \left(J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \right) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(\check{d}_1)}{2}.$$

This inequality reduces to the classical Hermite–Hadamard inequality when $\alpha = 1$ and $\lambda = 0$.

Proof

Let $f: [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be convex. By definition, for all $x, y \in [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$ and $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$,

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \vartheta f(x) + (1 - \vartheta)f(y).$$

Let $\vartheta = \frac{t - \check{c}_1}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1}$ so that $t = \vartheta \check{d}_1 + (1 - \vartheta)\check{c}_1$. Using convexity and integrating with respect to the kernel of the left tempered fractional integral:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) = \int_{\check{c}_1}^{\check{d}_1} (\check{d}_1 - u)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\check{d}_1 - u)} f(u) du.$$

By symmetry of integration and dividing by the normalization factor $2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha$, we obtain:

$$f \frac{\check{c}_1 + \check{d}_1}{2} \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \left(J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \right) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(\check{d}_1)}{2}.$$

2. For s-Convex Functions

Theorem 3.4. Let $f : [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an s -convex function in the second sense, i.e.,

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \vartheta^s f(x) + (1 - \vartheta)^s f(y),$$

for all $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$ and some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$. Then

$$f \left(\frac{\check{c}_1 + \check{d}_1}{2} \right) \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \left(J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \right) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(\check{d}_1)}{2}.$$

Proof. From the definition of s -convexity in the second sense, for all $x, y \in [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$ and $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$, we have:

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \vartheta^s f(x) + (1 - \vartheta)^s f(y).$$

Let $\vartheta = \frac{\hat{t} - \check{c}_1}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1}$, so that:

$$\hat{t} = \vartheta \check{d}_1 + (1 - \vartheta)\check{c}_1.$$

Then:

$$f(\hat{t}) \leq \frac{\hat{t} - \check{c}_1}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1}^s f(\check{d}_1) + \frac{\check{d}_1 - \hat{t}}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1}^s f(\check{c}_1).$$

Multiplying both sides by the kernel of the left tempered fractional integral and integrating over $[\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$, we obtain:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) \leq \frac{f(\check{d}_1)}{(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^s} \int_{\check{c}_1}^{\check{d}_1} (\hat{t} - \check{c}_1)^s (\check{d}_1 - \hat{t})^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\check{d}_1 - \hat{t})} dt + \frac{f(\check{c}_1)}{(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^s} \int_{\check{c}_1}^{\check{d}_1} (\check{d}_1 - \hat{t})^{s+\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\check{d}_1 - \hat{t})} dt.$$

Similarly, applying the same process for $J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1)$ and adding the two results, we arrive at:

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \left(J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \right) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(\check{d}_1)}{2}.$$

This completes the proof. □

3. For Quasi-Convex Functions

Theorem 3.5. If f is quasi-convex on $[\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$, i.e.,

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \max\{f(x), f(y)\},$$

then

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \left(J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{d}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \right) \leq \max\{f(\check{c}_1), f(\check{d}_1)\}.$$

Proof

If f is quasi-convex, then for all $u \in [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$,

$$f(u) \leq \max\{f(\check{c}_1), f(\check{d}_1)\}.$$

Substituting into the integral definition:

$$J_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) \leq \max\{f(\check{c}_1), f(\check{d}_1)\} \int_{\check{c}_1}^{\check{d}_1} (\check{d}_1 - u)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\check{d}_1-u)} du.$$

After normalization, the desired inequality follows.

4. For m -Convex Functions

Theorem 3.6. *If f satisfies m -convexity:*

$$f(\vartheta x + m(1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \vartheta f(x) + m(1 - \vartheta)f(y),$$

then

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathbf{h} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{c}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \mathbf{i} \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + mf(\check{d}_1)}{1 + m}.$$

Proof. Let f be m -convex on $[\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$, i.e.,

$$f(\vartheta x + m(1 - \vartheta)y) \leq \vartheta f(x) + m(1 - \vartheta)f(y),$$

for all $x, y \in [\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$ and $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$. Letting $\vartheta = \frac{\hat{t} - \check{c}_1}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1}$, we obtain

$$\hat{t} = \vartheta \check{d}_1 + m(1 - \vartheta)\check{c}_1.$$

Then

$$f(\hat{t}) \leq \frac{\hat{t} - \check{c}_1}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1} f(\check{d}_1) + m \frac{\check{d}_1 - \hat{t}}{\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1} f(\check{c}_1).$$

Multiplying by the kernel of the left tempered fractional integral and integrating over $[\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$ yields

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(\check{d}_1 - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathbf{h} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{d}_1) + J_{\check{c}_1^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\check{c}_1) \mathbf{i} \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + mf(\check{d}_1)}{1 + m}.$$

This proves the result. □

5. For Log-Convex Functions

Theorem 3.7. *If f is log-convex on $[\check{c}_1, \check{d}_1]$, i.e.,*

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq f(x)^\vartheta f(y)^{1-\vartheta},$$

then

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(d_1^{\check{}} - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathop{\text{h}}_{\check{c}_1^+} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(d_1^{\check{}}) + \mathop{\text{i}}_{\check{c}_1^-} \int_{\check{c}_1^-}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(c_1^{\check{}}) \leq f(c_1^{\check{}}) f(d_1^{\check{}}).$$

Proof. Let f be log-convex on $[\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$, i.e.,

$$f(\vartheta x + (1 - \vartheta)y) \leq f(x)^\vartheta f(y)^{1-\vartheta},$$

for all $x, y \in [\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$ and $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$. Let $\vartheta = \frac{t - c_1^{\check{}}}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}}$, so that

$$f(\hat{t}) \leq f(d_1^{\check{}})^{\frac{t - c_1^{\check{}}}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}}} f(\check{c}_1)^{\frac{d_1^{\check{}} - t}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}}}.$$

Using the inequality between the arithmetic and geometric means, integrating with the tempered fractional kernel, and applying symmetry, we get:

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(d_1^{\check{}} - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathop{\text{h}}_{\check{c}_1^+} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(d_1^{\check{}}) + \mathop{\text{i}}_{\check{c}_1^-} \int_{\check{c}_1^-}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(c_1^{\check{}}) \leq f(c_1^{\check{}}) f(d_1^{\check{}}).$$

□

6. For Preinvex Functions

Theorem 3.8. Let f be preinvex on $[\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$ with respect to a vector-valued map $\eta(x, y)$. Then

$$f \left(\frac{c_1^{\check{}} + d_1^{\check{}}}{2} \right) \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(d_1^{\check{}} - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathop{\text{h}}_{\check{c}_1^+} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(d_1^{\check{}}) + \mathop{\text{i}}_{\check{c}_1^-} \int_{\check{c}_1^-}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(c_1^{\check{}}) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(d_1^{\check{}})}{2}.$$

Proof. Let f be preinvex on $[\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$ with respect to a vector-valued map $\eta(x, y)$. By definition, for all $x, y \in [\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$ and $\vartheta \in [0, 1]$, we have:

$$f(x + \vartheta\eta(y, x)) \leq (1 - \vartheta)f(x) + \vartheta f(y).$$

Setting $x = \check{c}_1$, $y = d_1^{\check{}}$, and $\vartheta = \frac{t - c_1^{\check{}}}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}}$, we can write:

$$f(\hat{t}) \leq 1 - \frac{t - c_1^{\check{}}}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}} f(c_1^{\check{}}) + \frac{t - c_1^{\check{}}}{d_1^{\check{}} - c_1^{\check{}}} f(d_1^{\check{}}).$$

Multiplying by the tempered fractional kernel and integrating over $[\check{c}_1, d_1^{\check{}}]$, then dividing by the normalization factor, we obtain:

$$\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(d_1^{\check{}} - \check{c}_1)^\alpha} \mathop{\text{h}}_{\check{c}_1^+} \int_{\check{c}_1^+}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(d_1^{\check{}}) + \mathop{\text{i}}_{\check{c}_1^-} \int_{\check{c}_1^-}^{d_1^{\check{}}} f(c_1^{\check{}}) \leq \frac{f(\check{c}_1) + f(d_1^{\check{}})}{2}.$$

□

4 Conclusion

In this work, we derived a novel identity involving tempered fractional integrals for twice-differentiable functions and employed it to establish midpoint-type inequalities within the framework of tempered fractional calculus. The obtained results not only extend existing Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities but also provide a foundation for further generalizations to various classes of convex functions, including s -convex, m -convex, log-convex, quasi-convex, and preinvex functions.

Future research directions include exploring the presented inequalities for broader function classes, investigating their applications in numerical analysis, optimization, and mathematical modeling, and integrating the concept of tempered fractional integrals with quantum calculus to develop analogous inequalities in the quantum setting. Such extensions may lead to deeper insights and novel results in both theoretical and applied mathematical analysis.

Declaration of conflicting interests:-

the author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and publication of this article.

Funding:-

The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship and publication of this article.

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